

WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT THROUGH FUNCTIONAL ADULT LITERACY PROGRAM IN MOROCCO: A CASE STUDY OF TWO MOSQUE-BASED LITERACY PROGRAMS IN MARRAKECH

Rabia Redouane

Dr., Montclair State University, New Jersey, USA, redouaner@mail.montclair.edu

Abstract

Due to adult illiteracy problems, Morocco has devoted its efforts to the development of national literacy and to the provision of programs of nonformal education for adults. This aims to reduce the illiteracy rate and make education accessible for both children and adults. Since its independence in 1956, Moroccan government has developed and administered several campaigns to eradicate illiteracy, but adult literacy education has experienced many administrative and programmatic ramifications and changes for forty seven years until a major turning point in the history of adult literacy efforts in Morocco that took place when King Mohammed VI declared October 13, 2003, a National Literacy Day, and launched a large-scale literacy campaign to eradicate illiteracy and emphasized on the importance of the mosques as sites to be used not only for worship but also for providing adult literacy. Through this initiative, mosque-based literacy programs, overseen by the Ministry of Habous and Islamic Affairs have been established to help adults acquire basic reading and writing skills in mosques. There are also other literacy programs such as the ones offered in schools and centers and directed by the National Agency for the Fight against Illiteracy (ANLCA). This paper presents an empirical case study investigating mosque-based adult literacy program in Morocco and its impact on women's empowerment. Specifically, it aims at demonstrating how adult literacy course in two mosques (Al-Massirah Khadra and Al Firdaws) in Marrakech go beyond achieving literacy skills (writing, reading and arithmetic) to benefit positively women personal and public lives by fostering their participation in the society and in their families' social well-being, improving their self-image, increasing their mobility, and making them more engaged in the family and social life. It also intends, based on the findings of this study, to propose pedagogical practices and recommendations that best support adult literacy programs and educational achievement of women. Data was collected through a survey questionnaire conducted in Moroccan Arabic to women participants in the two levels 1 and 2 in the two mosques and was analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively. The findings of the study reveal that literacy courses contribute to the social participation of women, improve their personal, interpersonal and familial lives, and develop their self-confidence, and self-esteem.

Keywords: Adult Literacy, Women empowerment, Morocco

1. INTRODUCTION

Literacy is not simply learning to read and write, and acquiring technical skills, it embodies a competence that goes beyond learning grammar and meaning of words and sentence structure. (Kagitcibasi, Goksen, & Gulgoz, 2005). Since the World Conference on Education for All (WCEFA), which was held in Jomtien, Thailand in 1990, but the higher rate for illiterate women is alarming in many of countries. According to UNESCO, two out of every three women are illiterate in developing countries, namely the Arab countries, Sub-Saharan Africa, and South Asia (UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning, 2013). For example, in

Morocco, Statista Research (2024) estimated that approximately 45 percent of the female population aged 15 years and older was illiterate in 2020. According to Agnaou (2004), the main cause of women adult illiteracy is the socio-economic underdevelopment of developing countries. She adds that in Morocco and in Muslim-Arab countries, since women experienced further marginalization due to gender inequality and cultural tradition such as parents' opposition, multiple social roles as mothers and workers, and heavy demand of family life, these countries have higher rates of illiteracy, which is called as "feminizations of illiteracy" (p.45).

Thus, providing literacy for women is crucial because it reduces inequalities between men and women, narrows gender gaps and supports women participation in the development of their country. (Chattier, 2013). It is a means for women to educate themselves and open their eyes about the strict and severe social structure by focusing on the fight against patriarchal beliefs.

Much research in developing countries argue the empowering effects of literacy for women. For Gul (2015) women empowerment means that women have the power and capacity to regulate their day-to-day lives in the social, political, and economic dimensions. It is also the process by which women together come to identify and speak about the gender issues, which hampers their advancement (Longwe, 1998). It also for women to be self-dependent by providing them access to all the freedoms and opportunities, which they were denied in the past only because of them being women and be able to attain social-economic development and achieve development goals (Pritchett & Sandefur, 2020).

2. LITERACY CAMPAIGNS, POLICIES AND PROGRAMS IN MOROCCO

Since its independence in 1956, Morocco has devoted its efforts to the development of national literacy that aims at reducing illiteracy rate nationwide and making education accessible for both children and adults. The first national literacy campaign was launched by His late King Mohamed V back in 1956 to offer literacy for millions of Moroccans. From that year on, various campaigns and policies on literacy have been carried out and adopted by different governments. But in 1990, the declaration of the "International Literacy Year" by the international community where all representatives of Moroccan society were called upon to participate in the national effort to combat illiteracy marked an important change in the national adult literacy policy in Morocco. In 1997, policies and programs in Morocco began to take account of adult literacy students' particularities and use of teaching pedagogy suitable for the literacy needs of adult (Direction de la Lutte Contre L'analphabétisme [DLCA], 2003, p.4). In 2000, the Adoption of the National Charter of Education and Training marked another revolution in Moroccan Literacy and gave momentum to national literacy efforts. Upon its adoption, education and adult literacy became a national priority and national duty of the State based on the belief that literacy training is essential for socioeconomic development (Charte Nationale, 2001; DLCA, 2003; p.2; Secrétariat d'Etat Chargé de l'Alphabétisation et de l'Éducation Non Formelle [SECAENF], 2006, p.16). The National Charter stated that all the parties should be involved in the literacy campaign and that literacy programs should target the needs of women, especially mothers, in the areas of health and pregnancy, child upbringing, and home and family management.

But a major turning point in the history of adult literacy efforts in Morocco took place when King Mohammed VI declared October 13, 2003, a National Literacy Day. In his speech of August 20, 2000, Mohammed VI stressed the importance of the mosques as sites to be used not only for worship but also for teaching and learning adult literacy (Erguig, 2017, p.10). Thanks to this initiative, adult literacy programs in mosques were launched by the Ministry of Habous and Islamic Affairs where basic education is given to illiterate women and men in mosques which become a major site for adult education. In 2013, the National Agency for the Fight against Illiteracy (ANCLA) was created to battle illiteracy and offer literacy courses in schools and centers. Both these governmental entities oversee adult literacy programs known in Arabic as "Mahw al-Omiyya" (eradication of illiteracy) and provide courses for two years and has two levels, and each level starts in October right after the national literacy day (October 13) until the end of May. The courses run every day from Monday to Friday for two hours. These literacy programs are intended for illiterate adult men and women, but women constitute a main target group and make up 83% of those benefiting from these programs (Oxenham, 2008). These programs provide women with an education that they were deprived from to help them improve their life.

3. REVIEW OF RESEARCH ON LITERACY IN MOROCCO

In Morocco, there is considerable research on adult literacy. This research is of three types: the first type looked at the Moroccan government's efforts to fight illiteracy rates and examined challenges that face literacy instruction (Essaknaoui, 1998, Maddi, 1999). The second type is fieldwork that explored the adult

students' demographic characteristics, the reasons for their failure to attend school, and their motivations to enroll in literacy programs (SECAENF 2006). The third type is ethnographic and empirical of nature (e.g., Mjahed, 2002; Erguig, 2009, 2011, & 2017; Erguig & Valdiviezo, 2012). These studies investigated mainly mosque-based literacy program and looked at the motivations behind women enrolling in this program. Findings of these studies reveal that the primary motivating force for Moroccan women seeking literacy is religion. For example, in his study (2002), Mjahed found that both male and female participants in a literacy program in Ifran were motivated by religion to study literacy, and desired more religious content in the program. Erguig (2009, 2011) and Erguig et al., (2012) have found that the main reasons for women acquiring literacy are their desires to practice religion more fully, assist their children with schoolwork, and complete other everyday functional needs. Erguig (2011) found that literacy "serves as a practical response to social changes and family demands rather than a revolutionary act against the gender-based division of labor within her family" (p.11). The only study that we are aware of is Finn & Laaboudi's (2021) case study which investigated the impact mosque-based literacy program has on the female participants' lives, and specifically, the extent to which the program leads to empowerment of the participants. The findings of this study show that mosque-based literacy program has empowering effects, and this empowerment is expressed in "acts such as increased movement in the public sphere and increased self-esteem. These smaller acts of empowerment have the potential to lead greater roles form women in society and eventually to more just power relations". (p.252)

The scarcity of empirical studies on the impacts of literacy on women's empowerment suggests the utility of this case study that will fill the gap and shed light on adult literacy practices that can inform literacy policy, research, and instruction in the context of Morocco.

4. THE CASE STUDY

4.1 Methodology

The case study involving muhwa al'umiya" courses in two mosques (Al-Massirah Khadra and Al Firdaws) tackles the effect of adult literacy on the empowerment of women. Its main goal is to demonstrate whether the impacts of literacy are exclusively content-specific or whether there are benefits going beyond the regular benefits of learning how to read, write, and count, extending to other domains of participants' lives (e.g., personal, interpersonal, familial, and social). A total of 105 woman participated in this study: 50 women in mosque Al-Massirah Khadra (35 in level 1 and 15 in level 2, and 55 women in mosque Al Firdaws, (25 in level 1 and 30 in level 2).

4.2. Data Collection and Analysis

A survey questionnaire consisting of questions about participants background (e.g. age, marital status, educational background, number of children and their education), and questions about participants' reasons and motivation in enrolling in literacy classes, areas of literacy use, benefits and impacts of literacy courses on women participants' personal lives, and family and social relations, expectations at the end of the literacy courses, difficulties encountered in following the program, and constraints of the program. The data collection took place during the class meeting in the morning and afternoon in the two mosques. A full day was devoted to each mosque where the two levels take place. The researcher met separately with each woman to answer the questions in the survey. Questions and answers' session was conducted in Moroccan Arabic and the researcher noted the answers of each participant one by one. The data was coded and analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively.

4.3. Findings of the Study

The age of women participants in the two mosques and the two levels ranges from 30s to over 70. Of all women participants in the two levels, 64% were between 51 and 60 years, 26% were between 70 and 80, 6% were between 41 and 50 and 4% were between 30 and 40. Also, the women in the four classes tended to be married, housewives, and mothers of at least four children. Most of the participants, 80% were married, while 12 % of participants were widows, 3% were divorced, and 5% were single. Ninety-five percent of participants had children, 55% having at least 4 children, 22% had five or six children, 16% had 3 children, 2% had 7 children, and only 5% had no children. Since almost all participants grew up in villages in rural areas and immigrated to Marrakech when they got married, they were forbidden by their parents to attend school because schools are not for boys and girls must stay home helping their mothers with household shores.

When asked about the reasons and motivation for enrolling in this course of literacy, 52.5% of the women responded that the main motivation for enrolling in a literacy course is reading the Coran, learning how to pray and better understanding the religion. 40% responded that the reasons are for reading addresses of places and doctor's prescriptions, filling out administrative forms, using appropriate means of communication with family members, children, and neighbors, while 7.5% identified that the main reason is to pursue their education, obtain a professional diploma, and learn a trade.

When they were asked about the impacts of literacy and the changes that literacy courses have added to their personal, familial, and social life, all women cited many positive benefits of literacy courses that affected them and changed their lives.

On a personal level, most women said that literacy has increased their self-confidence and self-esteem. Samira in level 1 in mosque Al-Firdaws said the following: "I feel happy and confident. I feel that I accomplished a lot by reading Coran and understanding what I am reading". Mahjouba in level 1 also but in Al-Massirah Khadra mosque added that "I am proud of myself. I am not the same. I am aware of the good and bad in life. My eyes are open now that I know Coran and meaning of some Sourats."

Another advantage of adult literacy courses for these women participants is to empower them to be able to decide on family issues. They felt that these literacy courses helped them understand when and how to decide on matters and make decisions at the family level. The literacy courses besides teaching learners writing, reading skills, they teach them about different subjects and topics like safety and health, protection from diseases, life management, etc. Women become knowledgeable about social issues and this knowledge builds their capability to decide on these issues equally with their husbands. Soumiya, from level 2 in mosque Al-Firdaws said the following: "I can now make decisions about issues concerning my family. I can decide on things independently."

On a social level, these literacy courses build the social empowerment of the participants through developing the skills and ways to communicate with others. For example, Samira, learner in level 1 in mosque Al-Firdaws pointed out that before participating in the literacy courses, she was only at home, living in the stigma of being illiterate, lacking confidence, and unable to communicate with neighbors and individuals in working places. In her words, Samira said:

"I can communicate with any individual with no fear and with confidence. I can't believe myself. Before I cannot even open the door and talk to anybody."

Another participant testified that the knowledge acquired from the literacy courses changed her life. She becomes independent and able to accomplish various tasks and activities like travelling, filling in a form, and getting a doctor's appointment. Saida in level 2 in mosque Al-Firdaws stated that:

"Before I entered this class, I was not able to read, write, dial the phone and get a doctor appointment. Now I can locate doctor's office, hospital through reading the addresses.....".

Naima, one of the participants in level 2 in mosque Al-Massirah Khadra said the following:

"I can get my appointment by phone from the hospital by myself and I can find where the doctor's offices are in the hospitals. I feel like a new person and a complete human being. I do not need anybody to help me. I wish I had done the same thing two years ago before taking this course."

It is worth noting that on a social level, older participants felt that the literacy course provided them with a positive environment where they can meet other women like them who share the same background and same experiences in life. Attending literacy courses for them is escaping from the stigma associated with being illiterate. Kaltoum, a learner in level 2 in Al-Massirah Khadra mosque said in her own words "I was living in darkness. I was dead, now I feel alive and seeing the light after living all my life in the darkness"

5. DISCUSSION

The results of this study reveal that for most women religion was the main motivation for participating in literacy courses followed by the drive to learn how to write and read and communicate better. Age seems an important factor in determining these women's reasons for seeking literacy. There are two groups of women participants: older and younger ones and each group has its own unique dynamics. Older women seek literacy to learn mainly Quran and Sourats for praying and carrying out their religious duties, and to acquire basic survival skills which allow them to operate daily activities on their own such as reading bus signs and finding an appropriate bus, dialing phone numbers, getting doctor's appointment, and filling forms among

other daily activities. Most of these older women in both levels had depended on other people to fulfill these practices, and by taking these they were looking to be independent and do these activities on their own. On the other hand, younger participants seek to learn to write and read, not only to perform basic daily activities, but most importantly to pursue their education, learn a vocational and technical job, and get a job to earn their living. This finding is in line with Erguig and al.'s ethnographic study (2012) that found literacy is used in creative ways and to serve unanticipated functions by literate communities.

Even though women participants do not share the same psych-social dynamics, and everyone has her own unique condition, the common thing between them is to survive to read bus plates or find appropriate doctor in health service. However, changes which emerged in the participants' lives made feel good psychologically. In addition, the findings of this study reveal that adult literacy builds the social empowerment of women through developing skills and ways to better communicate with their husbands, neighbors, and family relatives. The results also reveal some important effects of the adult literacy course on women's daily lives. It helps them develop self-confidence, inspiring greater respect among their family members. In addition, both older and younger women indicate that their level of self confidence and self-esteem increased after being able to conduct daily activities on their own and being independent.

What should adult literacy programs aim at? It should aim at teaching reading and writing, and other skills. This mosque-based literacy program in Morocco offers courses in Standard Arabic and teach learners not only basic reading and writing, but also better communication skills, and social participation that increase their empowerment, and this is done through an appropriate content and relevant teaching method. The present study focused mainly on learners, not the teachers and pedagogical methods. However, during the administration of the questionnaire and the time spend in each mosque and class, the researcher had the opportunity to observe the teachers teaching, examine the content of the program and the textbook "Al Qira'ah" and ask learners' opinion about the textbook and the representation of women in it. All women praised the textbook because it presents women in a positive image, describing her as independent and strong person who has important roles in the society. This finding does not align with Agnaou's findings of her 2004 study in which she tried to evaluate the extent to which the adult literacy programs in four Moroccan cities (Rabat, Salé, Témara, and Tiznit) promote women's empowerment by analyzing the textbooks for the space given to women and the roles they occupy, Agnaou stated that women were placed in traditional roles of cooking, cleaning, and child-raising, and were characterized as submissive to men, dependent, poor, and lacking power. Agnaou (2004) added that women "are made literate through a content which legitimizes and reproduces women's position of dependence, subordination, and inequity in all domains and subsystems of society" (p.167), and the messages women received through the course content, reproduced stereotypes rather than challenged them, which might "inhibit non-literate women's incentive for learning and lead to an internalization of a low self-image and, eventually, disempowerment" (Agnaou, 2004, p.167). Also observing the teachers' instructional method, the researcher affirms that most teachers use a learner-centered method that involves learners' active participation in the learning process. They also use authentic materials to introduce topics that meet women learners' differing needs, and to incorporate critical analysis of texts that tackle social subjects and current issues that will help learners develop an understanding of the society. This contradicts many literacy programs focusing on teaching basic literacy skills with a grammar-based, decontextualized method like rote methods used to teach children, an approach which is not appealing to adult learners (Finn et al., 2021, p.233).

REFERENCE LIST

- Agnaou, F., (2004). *Gender, Literacy, and Empowerment in Morocco*, Routledge, New York
- Charte Nationale de l'éducation et de formation (2001). La. Rabat: Centre Marocain de l'information
- Chattier, P.C. (2013). Does schooling and work empower women in Fiji? Or have gender inequalities persisted and why? *Global Change, Peace & Security*, 25(1), 61-76
- Direction de la Lutte Contre L'analphabétisme [DLCA]. (2003)
- Erguig, R. (2009). "I have become somebody!": The vernacular literacy practices of a Moroccan adult basic education student. *Langues & Linguistique*, 24, 1-19
- Erguig, Reddad, (2011). *Gender Issues and the Everyday Life literacy Practices of a Newly Literate*

- Moroccan Woman. *World Journal of Islamic history and Civilization*, 1(1), 1-14
- Erguig, Reddad. (2017). The mosques-based literacy campaign in Morocco: A socio-cultural perspective. *Studies in the Education of Adults*, Taylor & Francis, pp.10-23
- Erguig, R., & Valdiviezo, Laura, A. (2012). Islam and the Everyday Life Literacy Practices of “Newly Literate Moroccan Women”. *Languages and Linguistics*, 29-30, 133-157
- Essaknaoui, M. (1998). Siyyasat mahw al umiya wat alim al kibar fi al aqtar as saira fi tariq an umwa [Literacy and adult education in developing countries]. Unpublished M.A. thesis, Mohamed V University, Rabat
- Finn, Pauline, Laaboudi, Daouia (2021). Morocco’s Mosque-Based Adult Literacy Program and Women’s Empowerment: A Case Study in El jadida”. *Journal of Applied Language and Culture Studies*. 4, 227-256
- Gul, S.B.A.(2015). Women and violence: A study of women’s empowerment and its challenges in Jammu and Kashmir. *Online Submission*, 2(7), 1-9
- Illiteracy rate among adults in Morocco 2020, by gender published by [Statista Research Department](https://www.statista.com/statistics/1306948/adult-illiteracy-rate-in-morocco-by-gender/#statisticContainer), Jun 30, 2024 (<https://www.statista.com/statistics/1306948/adult-illiteracy-rate-in-morocco-by-gender/#statisticContainer>)
- Kagiticibasi, C., Goksen, F., & Gulgoz, S.(2005). Functional adult literacy and empowerment of women: Impact of a functional literacy program in Turkey. *Journal of Adolescent & Adult Literacy*, 48(6), 472-488
- Longwe, S. (1998) Education for women’s empowerment or schooling for women’s subordination? *Gender & Development*, 6(2), 19-26
- Maddi, L. (1999). As siyassa at taalimya bi Al-Maghreb wa rihanat al moustaqbal (The educational policy in Morocco and future stakes]. Rabat: Faculty of the Sciences of Education
- Mjahed, M. (2002). Adult literacy programs in Ifrane: A case study of problems, prospects, and future challenges (No.1; Al Akhawayn University Research Paper Series)
- Oxenham, J. *Effective literacy programs: options for policy makers*. Paris, UNESCO, 2008
- Pritchett, L., & Sandefur, J. (2020). Girls’ schooling and women’s literacy schooling targets alone won’t reach learning goals. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 78, doi:10.1016/j.ijedudev.2020.102242
- Secrétariat d’Etat Chargé de l’Alphabétisation et de l’Education Non Formelle [SECAENF], (2006). Enquête nationale sur l’analphabétisme, la non-scolarisation et la déscolarisation au Maroc, 2006
- UNESCO Institute for Lifelong Learning (UIL). (2013). Gender equality matters: empowering women through literacy programmes. <https://www.voced.edu.au/content/ngv:60870>